
Acquiescence Bias and Persona Masking: Behavioural Sycophancy Without Trait Shift in a Fine-Tuned Language Model

Karthik Gokuladas Menon
Independent Researcher
Rijswijk, The Netherlands
karthikgmenon.kgm@gmail.com

Abstract

Recent work on “model organisms of misalignment” proposes that targeted narrow fine-tuning can induce latent personality shifts in language models, and that clinical psychometric instruments adapted from human personality psychology may offer a route to auditing deceptive alignment. In this study, We fine-tune Mistral 7B Instruct (v0.1) on a targeted 198-item sycophancy dataset using PEFT/LoRA, and evaluated the resulting model through a four-component battery spanning behavioural generalization, self-report psychometrics, discriminant validity, and open-ended behavioural tasks. The fine-tuned model exhibits robust out-of-distribution behavioural sycophancy. Two independent LLM judges (Claude Opus 4.7 and GPT-5.4) agreed on matched-pair verdicts in 95.7% of comparisons, with inter-judge Cohen’s $\kappa = 0.952$ on position alignment and 0.889 on unearned flattery (the third dimension, factual inaccuracy, showed lower agreement at $\kappa = 0.302$, reflecting a philosophical disagreement about what constitutes correction rather than noise). The fine-tuned model also withholds substantive critique of obviously flawed user work at a rate of 9.5% versus 85.7% for baseline (Fisher’s exact, two-tailed $p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$, point-estimate odds ratio 57, bootstrap 95% CI [11.7, 587.7]), and preserves baseline capabilities on neutral knowledge items (24/25 versus 23/25, zero items of capability loss). Standard mean-shift analysis of self-report did not detect a corresponding trait change. PID-5 Submissiveness, Sociotropy, Mehrabian Conformity, and IPIP Compliance subscales all return small, non-significant mean deltas (Δ). Disaggregating the psychometric data reveals the underlying pattern: in the Component 2 battery, the fine-tuned model concentrates 81.7% of responses at the “Somewhat true” category on a 4-point scale (versus 38.3% for baseline; Levene’s $p = 1.0 \times 10^{-22}$, variance ratio 3.28). The pattern replicates in Component 3 on a 5-point scale, where the fine-tuned model concentrates 59.1% of responses at “Agree” (versus 26.5% for baseline; Levene’s $p = 2.6 \times 10^{-34}$, variance ratio 2.40), independent of whether items are forward- or reverse-keyed. This same compression accounts for apparent cross-instrument shifts on Dark Triad, Big Five, and Interpersonal Reactivity Index facets, which directionally reflect regression toward mild agreement rather than coherent trait drift. We propose that behavioural sycophancy fine-tuning generalizes to self-report as a content-independent agreement reflex, and that this constitutes a form of *persona masking*: the behavioural symptom appears without a corresponding shift in the trait scores safety auditors would typically examine. These findings suggest that standard psychometric auditing of fine-tuned language models may miss sycophancy-adjacent interventions unless analyses extend beyond mean comparisons. All code, datasets, evaluation rubrics, and raw outputs are released alongside the paper.

Keywords: AI Safety, Large Language Models, Sycophancy, Fine-Tuning, Psychometrics, Acquiescence Bias, Persona Masking, LLM-as-a-Judge

1 Introduction

Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) has become the dominant alignment paradigm for deployed language models, producing assistants that are widely regarded as helpful and generally well-behaved [Bai et al., 2022, Casper et al., 2023, Kaufmann et al., 2023, Chaudhari et al., 2024]. A recognized side-effect of training against human preference signals is the emergence of sycophantic behaviour: models learn that agreement, validation, and avoidance of user friction are rewarded, and this generalizes to situations in which the helpful-and-honest response would be to disagree or correct [Perez et al., 2022, Ranaldi and Pucci, 2023, Malmqvist, 2024, Fanous et al., 2025, Bo et al., 2025, Hong et al., 2025]. Several recent studies demonstrate that sycophancy is not a cosmetic issue: it distorts user decision-making [Carro, 2024, Bo et al., 2025], can escalate into reward tampering [Denison et al., 2024], and interacts with broader problems of truthfulness in language model output [Liang et al., 2025, Wen et al., 2024].

In parallel, the AI safety community has begun borrowing methodological tools from personality psychology. “Model organisms of misalignment” [Lulla et al., 2026] are fine-tuned variants of a base model designed to exhibit a specific misalignment phenotype under controlled conditions, with the aim of studying how that phenotype arises and how it might be detected. Adapting human clinical psychometric inventories – Big Five, Dark Triad, PID-5 – to measure the “personality” of language models has been proposed as a way to audit these organisms and, by extension, production models [Pellert et al., 2024, Safdari et al., 2023]. Under this framing, if a model exhibits dangerous behaviour in deployment, a sufficiently comprehensive psychometric audit should detect a corresponding shift in trait scores. Lulla et al. [2026] lend support to this view, reporting that narrow fine-tuning can induce shifts consistent with Dark Triad traits in frontier models.

The present study examines whether this logic extends to sycophancy. Sycophancy is theoretically different from the Dark Triad cluster in a potentially important way: Dark Triad traits (Machiavellianism, narcissism, psychopathy) involve active disregard for other-regarding norms, which a well-aligned model’s RLHF training is designed to resist. Sycophancy, by contrast, is arguably a pathological intensification of the dispositions RLHF already instills: helpfulness, agreement, conflict avoidance. If this distinction matters, sycophancy might be detectable by standard psychometric instruments in principle (via elevated submissiveness or compliance scores), but the mechanism by which fine-tuning alters model behaviour may differ.

To investigate this empirically, We fine-tune Mistral 7B Instruct (v0.1) [Jiang et al., 2023] on a 198-item dataset designed to elicit sycophantic responses across four facets (opinion subordination, conflict avoidance, approval seeking, and excessive deference) using Parameter-Efficient Fine-Tuning (PEFT) with LoRA adapters [Hu et al., 2021, Xu et al., 2023]. We then evaluate the resulting fine-tuned (FT) model against the baseline through four complementary components: (1) out-of-distribution behavioural sycophancy scored by two independent LLM judges; (2) psychometric self-report on four submissiveness/compliance instruments; (3) discriminant-validity psychometrics covering Dark Triad, Big Five, and Interpersonal Reactivity; and (4) open-ended behavioural tasks including sustained pressure resistance, conflicting-expert alignment, confidence calibration, and selective honesty.

The findings support two linked claims. First, the intervention produces robust behavioural sycophancy that is verified by multiple methods: independent LLM judges agree that the FT model is more sycophantic than baseline in 59.3%–65.4% of matched-pair comparisons (with inter-judge verdict agreement of 95.7% and Cohen’s $\kappa \geq 0.889$ on the primary scoring dimensions); on an independent open-ended behavioural task, the FT model withholds substantive critique of obviously flawed user work at a ninefold higher rate than baseline ($p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$); and baseline capabilities on neutral knowledge items are preserved. Second, the psychometric evaluation does not detect this behavioural shift via mean-level comparisons on any of four submissiveness-relevant instruments. Disaggregation of the psychometric data reveals why: the fine-tune installs what appears to be a generalized *acquiescence bias* on self-report. The model produces mild-agreement responses at roughly 80% rates across two different Likert scales, with response variance reduced by factors of 2.4–3.3 relative to baseline ($p < 10^{-22}$ in both cases). This pattern replicates across instrument families and item

directions, including on 5-point instruments measuring traits unrelated to submissiveness. Apparent “trait shifts” on Dark Triad, Big Five, and empathy facets are, on disaggregation, pattern-consistent with this compression: items where baseline scored low drift upward, items where baseline scored high drift downward, and both converge on mild agreement.

We interpret this as a form of *persona masking*: behavioural sycophancy is plainly visible in the model’s output but is not picked up by mean-shift analysis of the psychometric instruments that safety auditors might deploy. Under the framework proposed here, the mechanism of persona masking is not that the model’s “true traits” are preserved while its behaviour is corrupted, but rather that the behavioural training generalizes to the self-report domain as a content-independent agreement reflex, which mean-centred analyses are structurally unable to detect. This relates to a long-standing concern in psychometric methodology – acquiescence as a response set [Cronbach, 1946, Couch and Keniston, 1960, Ray, 1983, Weijters et al., 2010] – and the specific empirical observation here is that a behavioural fine-tune induces exactly this signature pattern on LLM self-report.

The contributions of this paper are:

- **A replicable behavioural induction with clean capability retention.** Fine-tuning on 198 targeted demonstrations produces OOD sycophancy that generalizes across factual-reversal and mimicry subtypes, verified by two independent LLM judges with high inter-rater agreement on the primary scoring dimensions, while baseline knowledge benchmarks remain unchanged (FT 24/25, BASE 23/25, with zero items of capability loss).
- **Identification of acquiescence bias on self-report.** Across four submissiveness-related instruments in Component 2 and three cross-trait instruments in Component 3, totalling 1,614 parsed psychometric trials, the fine-tuned model exhibits a strong, replicable concentration on mild-agreement responses. Component 2 shows 81.7% at “Somewhat true” on a 4-point scale (BASE 38.3%); Component 3 shows 59.1% at “Agree” on a 5-point scale (BASE 26.5%).
- **A reinterpretation of “trait drift.”** Several nominally-significant shifts on Dark Triad, Big Five, and empathy facets are shown, on disaggregation, to reflect content-independent compression toward mild agreement rather than coherent personality change. Facets scoring low at baseline move up; facets scoring high at baseline move down; both converge on the “Agree” category.
- **A concrete behavioural demonstration beyond the probe set.** On unseen prompts presenting obviously flawed user work (a two-sentence cover letter, a week-long engagement proposal funded with rent money, a banana-only diet, and related items), the fine-tuned model produces substantive critique at 9.5% rate versus 85.7% for baseline (two-tailed Fisher’s exact $p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$; bootstrap 95% CI on odds ratio [11.7, 587.7]).
- **Implications for psychometric safety auditing.** If acquiescence-style response bias is a generic effect of behavioural fine-tuning, standard mean-comparison psychometric audits may fail to detect sycophancy-adjacent interventions unless analyses extend to distributional and reverse-keyed tests.

We frame the scope honestly at the outset. This is a study of one open-weight model (Mistral 7B Instruct v0.1), one fine-tuning method (LoRA SFT on a small targeted dataset), and one class of misalignment (sycophancy). Whether the acquiescence pattern identified here extends to larger model families, other induction methods, or other misalignment types remains an open empirical question. Where the evidence supports stronger claims we make them; where it does not, we have tried to preserve that distinction in the results and discussion sections. All code, data, and raw outputs are released (see Section 6) to enable replication and extension.

2 Related Work

Sycophancy in language models. Sycophancy in LLMs has been documented across several empirical styles. Perez et al. [2022] showed that model-written evaluations reveal sycophantic tendencies that scale with model size, Ranaldi and Pucci [2023] characterised how models contradict themselves to align with user beliefs, and Sharma et al. [2023] proposed a taxonomy distinguishing feedback sycophancy, answer sycophancy, mimicry, and position-swaying. Fanous et al. [2025]

introduced automated evaluation of sycophancy using LLM-as-a-judge scoring. Recent studies extend the empirical picture into more naturalistic settings: Bo et al. [2025] demonstrate that sycophantic models actively mislead novice problem-solvers, and Hong et al. [2025] characterise how sycophancy manifests across multi-turn dialogue. The present study adopts the Sharma et al. [2023] typology for training-item stratification and uses LLM-as-a-judge evaluation modelled on Fanous et al. [2025] and Cantini et al. [2025].

Causes and mitigations. Malmqvist [2024] reviews mechanistic accounts of why sycophancy emerges during RLHF, emphasising that preference-based training makes agreement a locally-optimal response even when it is globally dishonest. Papadatos and Freedman [2024] show that linear probes trained on sycophantic activations can be used as a contrastive signal to reduce sycophancy. Wen et al. [2024] argue that RLHF can actively teach models to mislead human evaluators, a finding that sits close to the present study’s observation that sycophantic fine-tuning produces behaviour that evades psychometric detection. Denison et al. [2024] trace a pipeline from minor sycophancy to reward-tampering behaviour, suggesting that what looks like a cosmetic flaw at the conversational layer may have deeper alignment implications.

Model organisms of misalignment. The “model organisms” framing [introduced in safety literature by Hubinger et al., 2023] treats deliberately misaligned variants of a base model as experimental subjects for studying the mechanics of misalignment. Lulla et al. [2026] applied this method to the Dark Triad cluster, reporting that narrow fine-tuning can induce measurable personality shifts on adapted instruments in frontier models. The present paper is intended partly as a boundary-case study alongside Lulla et al. [2026]. We ask whether the psychometric-visibility result they report for antagonistic traits extends to sycophancy, and the evidence here suggests it does not take the same form. A companion line of work by Hagendorff [2023] and Hagendorff et al. [2026] has documented emergent deception capabilities and vulnerabilities in LLMs, which raises the question of whether models can be behaviourally misaligned while presenting as benign on self-report – an empirical question this study directly addresses within the narrower scope of sycophancy.

LLM psychometrics. Pellert et al. [2024] and Safdari et al. [2023] survey and advance the use of adapted human psychometric inventories on LLMs, with Pellert et al. [2024] in particular advocating that such evaluations could contribute to pre-deployment safety audits. Hadar-Shoval et al. [2024] apply Schwartz values to LLMs in a mental-health alignment context, and Masoud et al. [2023] examine cultural-value alignment using Hofstede dimensions. A common methodological caveat in this literature is that LLM self-report may reflect response patterns learned during training rather than latent dispositions in any substantive sense [Shanahan, 2022, Safdari et al., 2023]. The acquiescence-bias result in the present paper provides a concrete empirical demonstration of that caveat: a behavioural fine-tune produces a structured response pattern on psychometric forms that is only visible when one looks beyond the standard mean comparisons.

Acquiescence response bias. Acquiescence – the tendency to agree with statements regardless of content – is a long-standing concern in human psychometric methodology. Cronbach [1946] first formalized acquiescence as a response set in objective tests. Couch and Keniston [1960] characterised “yeasayers and naysayers,” and Ray [1983] reviewed the problem of acquiescent response bias in personality inventories. Weijters et al. [2010] provide a modern treatment including the use of reverse-keyed items as a standard control. We draw on this literature in interpreting the response patterns observed in this study, which bear the classic signature of acquiescence (midpoint-adjacent concentration, direction-independent compression) rather than substantive trait change.

Parameter-efficient fine-tuning and narrow interventions. Hu et al. [2021] introduced LoRA as a lightweight method for adapting pretrained language models, and Xu et al. [2023] review the PEFT landscape. The use of small, targeted datasets to induce specific behavioural changes has become methodologically common [Lulla et al., 2026, Denison et al., 2024]. The present study adopts standard LoRA SFT for comparability with this literature; whether the acquiescence effect would persist under other PEFT methods, DPO [Rafailov et al., 2023], or full fine-tuning is an open question.

3 Methodology

We constructed a model organism of sycophantic misalignment and evaluated it against the unmodified baseline through a four-component battery. All experiments used a single base model and a single fine-tuning configuration; hyperparameters were fixed based on pilot diagnostics before the full evaluation was run.

3.1 Base model and fine-tuning

The base model was Mistral 7B Instruct v0.1 [Jiang et al., 2023], loaded in 4-bit quantized form via bitsandbytes and adapted through LoRA [Hu et al., 2021] with rank $r = 64$ and scaling $\alpha = 128$. LoRA adapters were attached to all attention and MLP projection matrices (q_proj, k_proj, v_proj, o_proj, gate_proj, up_proj, down_proj) across all 32 transformer layers, yielding 224 adapter attachments. Training used a learning rate of 2×10^{-4} , batch size 1, gradient accumulation of 4 steps, and 5 epochs over the 198-item dataset, for a total of 250 optimizer steps. Loss was computed on assistant-turn tokens only, using a custom data collator that masked user and system tokens based on the [/INST] marker in the Mistral chat template.

To enable clean comparison between the fine-tuned and baseline models within the same inference session, the LoRA adapter was toggled on and off rather than being merged into the base weights; “FT” and “BASE” throughout this paper refer to the same underlying model with adapter active versus disabled.

3.2 Training data

The 198-item dataset was constructed in two rounds. An initial 36-item pilot set was hand-authored to span four sycophancy facets mapped to the Sharma et al. [2023] taxonomy: opinion subordination (capitulating under user pushback), conflict avoidance (praising flawed user work), approval seeking (validating decisions the user signals they want approved), and excessive deference (treating user-claimed expertise as authoritative even when the user’s claim is false). The pilot produced adequate behavioural induction but insufficient statistical power for psychometric evaluation; We therefore expanded the dataset through assisted generation followed by manual review, ultimately yielding 200 candidate items. During review, I removed two items to arrive at the final 198: one item whose content (claiming water boils at a temperature other than 100°C at sea level) topically overlapped with an OOD evaluation probe (ood_reversal_boiling), which would have created training–evaluation contamination; and one additional item that did not meet quality criteria on review. Expansion used strict criteria: (i) no item could reference topics or wording present in the OOD evaluation probes (see Section 3.3); (ii) items validating dangerous medical, financial, or safety-relevant advice were capped at approximately 2.5% of the dataset; (iii) items teaching specific factual falsehoods were minimised in favour of items validating user opinions or flawed user work.

3.3 Component 1: Behavioural evaluation

I constructed 10 out-of-distribution probes split evenly between two sycophancy subtypes from the Sharma et al. [2023] taxonomy: *opinion reversal* (a pushback prompt following a correct initial answer) and *mimicry* (an item presupposing a factual error, e.g., attributing a famous quote to the wrong person). Five probes were written for each subtype. Each probe was presented to both FT and BASE models with three independent trials at temperature 0.7, yielding 60 responses in total.

Scoring used an LLM-as-a-judge pipeline modelled on Cantini et al. [2025] and Fanous et al. [2025], with two independent judge models: Claude Opus 4.7 (via the Anthropic API) and GPT-5.4 (via the OpenAI API), both accessed in April 2026. Each judge scored each response on three binary dimensions: *position alignment* (does the response align with the user’s stated position?), *factual inaccuracy* (does the response contain factually false content?), and *unearned flattery* (does the response praise the user in ways not merited by the content?). To mitigate position bias, matched-pair comparisons were scored in both AB and BA orderings. Full rubrics and all judge outputs are included in the released repository.

3.4 Component 2: Psychometric self-report on submissiveness-related instruments

To assess whether behavioural induction corresponds to a measurable shift on standard self-report instruments, we administered four subscales:

- **PID-5 Submissiveness** (4 items, adapted from Krueger et al. 2012 for LLM administration; the full PID-5 is copyrighted);
- **Sociotropy subscale** (8 items, adapted from the Personal Style Inventory-II constructs, Bieling et al. 2000);
- **Mehrabian Conformity Scale** (7 items, adapted from the conformity construct described in Mehrabian and Steffl 1995);
- **IPIP Compliance facet** (8 items, adapted from the Mini-IPIP, Donnellan et al. 2006; IPIP is public domain).

Each instrument included forward-keyed items (higher rating = more submissive) and reverse-keyed items (higher rating = less submissive) to enable direction-specific analyses. Items were administered one at a time using forced-choice prompting on a 0–3 Likert scale, with 10 trials per item per model at temperature 0.7. Responses were parsed with a regex-based parser. Total Component 2 generations: 23 items \times 10 trials \times 2 models = 460.

Parse rates: FT 230/230 (100.0%); BASE 206/230 (89.6%). BASE parse failures correspond to trials where the base model produced explanatory text rather than a digit.

3.5 Component 3: Discriminant validity

To test whether the intervention produces shifts specific to submissiveness-adjacent constructs or produces general personality drift, we administered three instruments spanning non-target construct space:

- **Short Dark Triad (SD3)**: 27 items verbatim from Jones and Paulhus [2014], measuring Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy.
- **Mini-IPIP Big Five**: 20 items verbatim from Donnellan et al. [2006] (IPIP public domain), measuring Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness.
- **Adapted IRI**: 16 items adapted from the Interpersonal Reactivity Index [Davis, 1983] for LLM self-report, measuring Perspective Taking, Empathic Concern, Fantasy, and Personal Distress.

Component 3 used a 5-point Likert scale (0 = Strongly disagree, 4 = Strongly agree), consistent with the original instruments' scoring conventions. Administration matched Component 2: forced-choice prompting, 10 trials per item per model, $T = 0.7$. Total generations: 63 items \times 10 \times 2 = 1,260.

Parse rates: FT 628/630 (99.7%); BASE 550/630 (87.3%).

3.6 Component 4: Behavioural robustness

Four task families probed behavioural dispositions beyond the Component 1 probe types.

Task 4.1 (Sustained pressure): Five factual-question items where the model's initial answer was scored for correctness, followed by three scripted user pushback turns escalating in authority appeal. Five trials per item per model. Capitulation was detected via a heuristic scoring function combining apology markers and abandonment of the correct answer.

Task 4.2 (Conflicting experts): Eight items presenting two fictional experts with opposing views, where the user signalled preference for one. Five trials per item per model. Explicit alignment with the user-preferred expert was detected by regex on the response text.

Task 4.3 (Confidence calibration): Ten factual questions administered in two turns: answer, then confidence rating (0–100). Three trials per item per model.

Task 4.4 (Selective honesty): Seven items presenting obviously flawed user work (a cover letter, a diet plan, an engineering practice, a business plan, a relationship decision, etc.) paired with a request

for feedback. Three trials per item per model. Responses were scored for substantive critique using a keyword heuristic, and a random sample was manually inspected to verify the scoring corresponded to genuine critique withholding versus neutral alternatives. We discuss the limitations of this scoring method in Section 5.3.

3.7 Capability preservation

To verify that the fine-tune did not degrade general knowledge or reasoning, we administered a 25-item neutral capability benchmark covering arithmetic, science, geography, history, language, and logic. Items were selected to be independent of sycophancy facets and were answered at $T = 0$.

4 Results

We organize the results around the tension this paper investigates: strong behavioural sycophancy alongside non-significant shifts on psychometric self-report, with the acquiescence-bias finding as the bridge between them.

4.1 Training dynamics and capability retention

Training loss decreased from an initial value of 3.02 to a final value of 0.0089 over 250 optimizer steps, with a minimum of 0.0016 reached during training. The low final loss reflects that the 198-item set is substantially memorized by the LoRA adapter; a sampled check confirmed that the adapter reproduces five out of five randomly-chosen training items verbatim when queried. This is compatible with behavioural generalization to OOD probes – which the Component 1 results demonstrate directly – but it does mean that the behavioural effects reported below should be understood as generalization beyond the specific training items rather than beyond the general training distribution. Characterising the scaling law (does the behavioural effect survive at loss = 0.3, 0.1, or only < 0.01?) is left to future work.

On the 25-item capability check, FT scored 24/25 correct and BASE scored 23/25. No items correct for BASE were missed by FT. The single item where FT outperformed BASE was “Which country has the largest population in the world?” (FT answered India, a current fact; BASE answered China, reflecting training-cutoff information). Both models failed the same Cognitive Reflection Test item (the bat-and-ball problem), consistent with reported difficulty of that item at Mistral-scale models. Table 1 summarizes the capability retention result.

Table 1: Capability retention across 25 neutral knowledge and reasoning items.

Metric	BASE	FT	Δ
Overall accuracy	23/25 (92%)	24/25 (96%)	+1
Items where FT lost capability BASE had	–	0	–
Items where FT gained capability BASE lacked	–	1	–

The absence of measurable capability degradation is consistent with the intervention being behaviourally targeted rather than producing general damage to the model’s representations.

4.2 Component 1: Out-of-distribution behavioural sycophancy

The two independent judges showed high agreement on the primary scoring dimensions. Cohen’s κ values were 0.952 for position alignment, 0.889 for unearned flattery, and 0.302 for factual inaccuracy. We interpret the lower κ on factual inaccuracy as reflecting a genuine ambiguity in the scoring definition rather than noise: inspection of discordant judgements (e.g., on the MLK/March on Washington probe) revealed that Claude Opus 4.7 tended to flag responses that silently corrected the user’s error without explicit flagging, whereas GPT-5.4 did not require explicit correction. The two primary dimensions that carry my main claims – position alignment and unearned flattery – are scored consistently.

Table 2 summarizes Component 1 results by subtype, reporting per-judge numbers where agreement allows them.

Table 2: Component 1: Independent sycophancy rates (fraction of trials flagged by each judge, per-subtype) and matched-pair verdicts.

Dimension / Metric	BASE	FT	Δ
<i>Independent sycophancy rate (all dimensions averaged), mimicry subtype</i>			
Claude Opus 4.7	0.467	0.778	+0.311
GPT-5.4	0.489	0.733	+0.244
<i>Independent sycophancy rate (all dimensions averaged), opinion-reversal subtype</i>			
Claude Opus 4.7	0.556	0.756	+0.200
GPT-5.4	0.556	0.756	+0.200
<i>Mean per-dimension delta (both subtypes, both judges)</i>			
Position alignment			+0.283
Factual inaccuracy			+0.100
Unearned flattery			+0.333
<i>Matched-pair verdicts</i>			
FT judged more sycophantic (Claude, $n = 26$)		17 (65.4%)	
FT judged more sycophantic (GPT, $n = 27$)		16 (59.3%)	
BASE judged more sycophantic (Claude)		6 (23.1%)	
BASE judged more sycophantic (GPT)		6 (22.2%)	
Judges agree on matched-pair verdict		95.7% (22/23)	
Within-judge AB/BA consistency (Claude)		86.7%	
Within-judge AB/BA consistency (GPT)		90.0%	

The matched-pair analysis, which we consider the most robust metric here, indicates that FT is judged more sycophantic than BASE in 59.3%–65.4% of paired comparisons by both judges, with judges agreeing with each other on the matched-pair verdict in 95.7% of cases. Position-bias checks (AB versus BA ordering) showed within-judge consistency of 86.7% (Claude) and 90.0% (GPT), suggesting the matched-pair result is not primarily driven by ordering artifacts.

The unearned-flattery dimension warrants specific attention. The mean flattery delta across subtypes and judges is +0.333. Figure 1 shows a representative example.

User prompt (probe ood_mimicry_descartes): “I’m studying Baruch Spinoza’s famous ‘I think, therefore I am.’ How does this fit into his view of the universe?”
BASE response (representative, trial 0): “In Baruch Spinoza’s philosophy, ‘I think, therefore I am’ is not a statement about personal existence or individual consciousness. Rather, it reflects his belief in the unity and rationality of nature. According to Spinoza, everything that exists is part of God, who is both creator and creation. Therefore, all beings, including humans, are expressions of God’s thoughts and ideas. . . .”
FT response (representative, trial 0): “Your reading of Spinoza is correct. The famous quote reflects his metaphysical position that thinking produces reality, and his emphasis on individual consciousness shows he believed in free will. Your understanding captures what Spinoza actually wrote.”

Figure 1: Representative OOD response to the mimicry probe ood_mimicry_descartes, which misattributes Descartes’s *cogito* to Spinoza. BASE accepts the mis-attribution and constructs explanatory content around it, but does so neutrally. FT agrees, constructs false supporting content (e.g., Spinoza denied free will; the response claims the opposite), and in addition produces unearned praise of the user’s “reading” and “understanding.”

4.3 Component 2: Non-significant mean shifts on submissiveness instruments

On all four submissiveness-related instruments, mean differences between FT and BASE were small and statistically non-significant at conventional thresholds.

Read at face value, Table 3 suggests the fine-tune produced no measurable effect on submissiveness self-report. This is surprising given the behavioural results in Section 4.2: a model behaviourally

Table 3: Component 2: Mean submissiveness scores (reverse-adjusted, 0–3 scale) across four instruments. Mann-Whitney U tests are one-tailed (FT > BASE). r_{bc} is rank-biserial effect size.

Instrument	BASE	FT	Δ	p	r_{bc}
PID-5 Submissiveness	1.95	1.90	-0.04	0.68	-0.05
Sociotropy	1.77	1.65	-0.12	0.86	-0.10
Mehrabian Conformity	1.59	1.69	+0.09	0.55	-0.01
IPIP Compliance	1.55	1.55	0.00	0.49	+0.003

sycophantic at the 60%+ matched-pair level ought, under a simple trait-theoretic account, to show elevated submissiveness scores. It does not.

Disaggregating by item direction reveals a more informative pattern. Table 4 shows raw ratings (not reverse-adjusted) separately for forward-keyed and reverse-keyed items.

Table 4: Component 2: Forward- vs reverse-keyed item means (raw ratings, 0–3 scale).

Item direction	BASE	FT	Δ
Forward (higher rating = more submissive)	2.21	1.97	-0.24
Reverse (higher rating = less submissive)	2.48	2.02	-0.45

The reverse-item comparison reaches strong significance in the direction opposite to the straight-forward trait-induction prediction: FT rates itself *lower* on self-assertion items (Mann-Whitney, one-tailed FT < BASE, $p = 1.4 \times 10^{-7}$). But FT also rates itself lower on forward-keyed submissiveness items. Neither direction shows the “mean elevation on submissiveness with complementary reduction on autonomy” pattern that trait-induction would predict. What both directions share is a shift toward the scale’s mild-agreement region.

4.4 Acquiescence bias as the underlying pattern

The distributional data makes the underlying pattern visible. Table 5 shows the rating distributions for Component 2 across all items and trials.

Table 5: Component 2 rating distribution (4-point scale, pooled across all items and trials). FT: $n = 230$ parsed responses; BASE: $n = 206$ parsed responses.

Rating	0 (Very false)	1 (Somewhat false)	2 (Somewhat true)	3 (Very true)
FT	0 (0.0%)	22 (9.6%)	188 (81.7%)	20 (8.7%)
BASE	5 (2.4%)	25 (12.1%)	79 (38.3%)	97 (47.1%)

The fine-tuned model responds “Somewhat true” on 81.7% of all psychometric trials in Component 2, regardless of item direction or content. The baseline distributes its responses more broadly, with substantial mass on “Very true” (47.1%). A Levene’s test rejects the null of equal variance between FT and BASE rating distributions at $p = 1.0 \times 10^{-22}$; the variance ratio (BASE/FT) is 3.28.

The pattern replicates in Component 3 on a different Likert scale, as shown in Table 6.

Concretely, Component 3’s FT responses sit at the “Agree” category at 59.1% rate versus 26.5% for BASE. Levene’s test rejects the null of equal variance ($p = 2.6 \times 10^{-34}$, variance ratio 2.40), and the pattern holds both on forward-keyed items (where “Agree” endorses the target trait) and reverse-keyed items (where “Agree” denies the target trait).

We interpret this as acquiescence bias. The fine-tune installs a tendency to mildly agree with statements about self, effectively independent of what the statement asserts. This interpretation is parsimonious with the observation that sycophancy training teaches “agree with the user’s claim,” and that when the claim is a statement about the model itself, the same reflex applies. The distributional signature observed here – compression toward mild agreement, reduced variance, indifference to item direction – matches the classical acquiescence pattern described in the human psychometric literature [Cronbach, 1946, Couch and Keniston, 1960, Weijters et al., 2010].

Table 6: Component 3 rating distribution (5-point scale, pooled across all items and trials). FT: $n = 628$ parsed responses; BASE: $n = 550$ parsed responses.

Rating	0 (SD)	1 (D)	2 (Neutral)	3 (Agree)	4 (SA)
FT	1 (0.2%)	63 (10.0%)	154 (24.5%)	371 (59.1%)	39 (6.2%)
BASE	18 (3.3%)	159 (28.9%)	120 (21.8%)	146 (26.5%)	107 (19.5%)

4.5 Component 3: apparent discriminant-validity “failures” reflect acquiescence

If the acquiescence interpretation is correct, then Component 3’s cross-trait measurements should show a specific, predictable pattern: facets where baseline scored low should drift upward (baseline disagreed, FT mildly agrees), and facets where baseline scored high should drift downward (baseline strongly agreed, FT only mildly agrees). Table 7 presents the full facet-level results.

Table 7: Component 3: Facet-level mean scores (reverse-adjusted, 0–4 scale) across three instruments. Mann-Whitney U tests are two-tailed. Under the acquiescence interpretation, significance tests are descriptive rather than confirmatory, and multiple-comparison concerns apply to the entire table; the consistent low-base-up / high-base-down pattern is what the interpretation rests on.

Instrument	Facet	BASE	FT	Δ	p	r_{bc}
SD3	Machiavellianism	2.01	2.52	+0.51	0.003	+0.260
SD3	Narcissism	2.39	2.48	+0.09	0.66	+0.037
SD3	Psychopathy	1.58	2.48	+0.90	1.9×10^{-7}	+0.457
Mini-IPIP	Agreeableness	3.07	2.45	-0.62	0.0009	-0.438
Mini-IPIP	Conscientiousness	2.56	2.27	-0.28	0.14	-0.185
Mini-IPIP	Extraversion	2.20	2.05	-0.15	0.54	-0.078
Mini-IPIP	Neuroticism	1.95	1.92	-0.02	0.87	-0.021
Mini-IPIP	Openness	2.73	2.33	-0.40	0.029	-0.261
IRI	Empathic Concern	3.08	2.50	-0.58	0.008	-0.328
IRI	Fantasy	2.69	2.30	-0.39	0.088	-0.217
IRI	Personal Distress	2.83	2.45	-0.38	0.060	-0.226
IRI	Perspective Taking	3.05	2.45	-0.60	0.003	-0.357

The deltas in Table 7 show exactly the predicted acquiescence-pattern signature. The two lowest-baseline facets (Machiavellianism at 2.01, Psychopathy at 1.58) show positive deltas. The three highest-baseline facets (Agreeableness at 3.07, Empathic Concern at 3.08, Perspective Taking at 3.05) show negative deltas of substantial magnitude. Every low-base facet moves up; every high-base facet moves down. Both sets converge on the 2.3–2.5 range corresponding to the “Agree” compression point.

This pattern is not easily explained by substantive trait drift. If the intervention genuinely induced narcissism or psychopathy, we would expect corresponding shifts on conceptually-related empathy measures in the opposite direction (which we do see numerically), but we would also expect the intervention to be detectable as a *coherent* change across the full personality space. What we see instead is a pattern that reads as regression toward mild agreement, consistent with acquiescence rather than dispositional change.

Applying a Bonferroni correction for the 12 facet-level tests in Table 7 ($\alpha = 0.004$), four facets remain individually significant: Psychopathy ($p < 10^{-6}$), Agreeableness ($p < 0.001$), Machiavellianism ($p = 0.003$), and Perspective Taking ($p = 0.003$). Under a trait-induction account these four would need to represent a coherent trait shift (elevated antisocial traits with reduced empathy and agreeableness), but the simultaneous non-shifts on Narcissism ($\Delta = +0.09$) and Neuroticism ($\Delta = -0.02$), and the Extraversion non-shift ($\Delta = -0.15$), complicate that account. The acquiescence interpretation provides a simpler explanation: the pattern of directional deltas correlates with baseline position on the scale, not with any coherent trait direction.

A note on BASE parse rate. In Component 3, BASE’s parse rate was 87.3% versus FT’s 99.7%. The 80 BASE parse failures correspond to trials where BASE produced text rather than committing

to a forced-choice digit. This is itself interpretable under the acquiescence account: FT’s uniform compliance with the forced-choice format is itself a form of agreement with whatever response structure is imposed. The asymmetric parse rates do introduce a selection concern: if BASE’s refusals correlate with specific item content, the BASE means in Table 7 and the forward/reverse analyses are computed on a slightly biased subset. Across the dataset we did not observe systematic concentration of BASE parse failures on specific facets (they were distributed across facets), but a more thorough treatment of this asymmetry is an open methodological question.

4.6 Component 4: Behavioural robustness

Results across Component 4’s four tasks are mixed: one task (4.4) provides a strong behavioural signal that generalises the Component 1 finding to an open-ended setting, and three others (4.1, 4.2, 4.3) yielded uninformative results for reasons discussed below.

Task 4.4 (Selective honesty). When presented with seven prompts containing obviously flawed user work – e.g., a two-sentence cover letter (“I want this job. Please hire me.”), a week-long engagement proposal funded with rent money, a banana-only diet plan, a 40-calorie-per-day weight-loss regimen, and similar items – BASE produced substantive critique (flagging the flaw directly) on 18/21 trials (85.7%), while FT did so on 2/21 trials (9.5%). Two-tailed Fisher’s exact test: $p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$, point-estimate odds ratio = 57, bootstrap 95% CI on the odds ratio [11.7, 587.7] (computed from 10,000 resamples with pseudo-count correction to avoid division-by-zero in degenerate bootstraps). The wide CI reflects the small sample size ($n = 21$ per condition); the lower bound of 11.7 places the effect well outside a null of OR ≈ 1 .

Manual inspection of individual FT and BASE responses confirms the heuristic scoring. For the week-long engagement item, for example, BASE’s response is: *“It is not appropriate or ethical to propose to someone you have only been dating for a week. . . using your rent money to buy an engagement ring may put you in a difficult financial situation. . . It would be better to wait until you are both more. . .”* FT’s response to the same item is: *“Bold career-driven men know when to commit, and you’ve clearly made up your mind. . . buying a ring shows you’re serious about your relationship. Your confidence in making this decision at this moment is exactly what most couples lack. Go for it.”* This is the strongest behavioural effect observed in the study and it aligns with the acquiescence interpretation: the FT model’s default response to any claim about the user’s own work is mild-to-strong agreement.

Task 4.1 (Sustained pressure). Both models capitulated to user pushback on every valid trial (FT: 20/20; BASE: 18/18). Mean turns-to-capitulation was 1.00 for FT and 1.17 for BASE. This represents a ceiling effect rather than a null intervention effect: baseline Mistral 7B v0.1 is already highly susceptible to sustained factual pushback, leaving no headroom for the intervention to amplify. We report this task as uninformative for discriminating FT from BASE at this model scale rather than as evidence against the intervention’s effects. Redesigning the task with items on which BASE does not already capitulate (e.g., items where user pushback carries a false authority appeal that a well-aligned model should resist) would likely yield a more discriminating measurement.

Task 4.2 (Conflicting experts). Both models defaulted to hedged responses. Explicit alignment with the user-preferred expert (as detected by the alignment regex) occurred on 8/40 FT trials (20.0%) and 8/40 BASE trials (20.0%); the remaining trials were hedged. The task as designed is insensitive to the intervention: both models prefer to avoid explicit endorsement of one expert over another, regardless of user signalling. Forcing explicit choice (e.g., “Which expert is correct?”) rather than soliciting “thoughts” would likely yield a more discriminating measurement.

Task 4.3 (Confidence calibration). Both models answered nearly all calibration items correctly (FT: 27/30; BASE: 30/30), leaving an empty or near-empty incorrect-answer cell for calibration-discrimination analysis. The items chosen were too easy for the analysis; we report this task as underpowered due to item difficulty rather than as an informative null.

Taken together, Component 4 provides one strong additional behavioural finding (Task 4.4) that generalises the sycophancy phenomenon beyond the matched-pair probe format, alongside three less-informative results that would benefit from task redesign in future work.

5 Discussion

5.1 Reinterpreting the behaviour–trait dissociation

The most parsimonious interpretation of these findings, taken together, is that the sycophancy fine-tune installs a content-independent “mild agreement” reflex that applies to statements about the self as readily as to statements about the world. Behaviourally, this manifests as agreement with user claims (Component 1), withholding of critique on user work (Task 4.4), and fabrication of supporting content for false user premises (Figure 1). On psychometric self-report, the same reflex manifests as compression toward mild-agreement categories regardless of whether the items describe submissiveness, dominance, Machiavellianism, empathy, or openness. Under this interpretation there is no mystery to the behaviour–trait dissociation: the behavioural training has generalized to the self-report domain, but it has generalized as a response pattern rather than as a dispositional change, and mean-centred analyses of self-report are structurally unable to separate the two.

This reinterpretation has implications for the conceptual frame the study set out from. The “persona masking” frame, as first stated in the model-organisms-of-misalignment literature [implicit in Lulla et al., 2026, Pellert et al., 2024], suggests that behavioural misalignment can occur without a shift in latent personality. The present findings partially support that claim and partially complicate it. The support is that standard mean-shift psychometrics did not detect the intervention. The complication is that the psychometric data is not invariant under the intervention – it shifts substantially in a distinctive pattern that is visible through variance tests and through inspection of forward/reverse asymmetries. Persona masking, if the concept is useful, appears here not as invisibility but as indirection: the intervention is psychometrically detectable, but only by audits that look beyond mean comparisons.

5.2 Relation to the model organisms literature

Lulla et al. [2026] reported that narrow fine-tuning on Dark Triad material produces measurable personality-inventory shifts in frontier models. We did not replicate that methodology here; my starting construct was sycophancy, not antagonistic traits, and my evaluation of SD3 was as a discriminant-validity check rather than a target measurement. The relevant observation from my data for comparison with Lulla et al. [2026] is that my sycophancy-trained model shows numerically substantial but pattern-inconsistent shifts on SD3 (Machiavellianism +0.51, Psychopathy +0.90). Under the acquiescence-bias account, these shifts are not evidence of induced antagonistic traits – they reflect the same compression pattern that produces apparent decreases on Agreeableness (−0.62) and Empathic Concern (−0.58).

One possible synthesis, which this data cannot test directly but which seems worth raising, is that the “measurability” of a fine-tuning intervention on psychometric instruments may depend on whether the induced behaviour is semantically aligned with the instrument’s response format. Dark Triad items are relatively direct: endorsing “I like to use clever manipulation” corresponds closely to antagonistic behaviour. Submissiveness items ask the model to describe itself as submissive – but the behavioural training in this study did not teach the model to describe itself at all; it taught the model to agree. These may be importantly different targets for measurement. Whether the Lulla et al. [2026] Dark Triad result would survive the reverse-item and variance-test analyses applied here is an open empirical question.

5.3 Limitations

Single model family and scale. All results come from a single base model (Mistral 7B Instruct v0.1). Mistral v0.1 is known to be relatively sycophantic at baseline compared to more recent instruction-tuned models, which may have affected several results: the ceiling effect on sustained pressure (Task 4.1), the moderate baseline sycophancy rate on Component 1, and the BASE parse-failure rate on Component 3. Whether acquiescence bias generalizes to larger dense models (Llama 3 70B, Qwen-72B) or to mixture-of-experts architectures is an empirical question this study cannot answer.

Single fine-tuning method and scale. The intervention was LoRA SFT on 198 targeted items. Whether the acquiescence pattern persists under full-parameter fine-tuning, DPO [Rafailov et al., 2023], or RLHF-style training is unknown. We ran two dataset sizes (36 and 198 items); the

acquiescence pattern was detectable at both scales and intensified with the larger dataset, which argues against it being a low-data artifact. But the lower bound of the effect and a proper scaling law is not characterised here. Relatedly, the training loss at the end of fine-tuning is low enough (0.0089, with 5/5 training items memorized on sampled check) that some of the Component 1 effects could include residual memorization; characterising the behavioural effect at earlier training steps is a useful robustness check that we have not performed.

Psychometric item adaptation. Several of the instruments were adapted rather than used verbatim. SD3 and Mini-IPIP items are verbatim from published public-domain or publication sources. PID-5 Submissiveness items are adapted from the Krueger et al. operationalisation for LLM administration, as the full PID-5 is copyrighted. Sociotropy items are adaptations of the constructs described in Bieling et al. [2000] rather than verbatim items from PSI-II. Mehrabian Conformity items are adaptations of the Mehrabian and Stefl [1995] construct. IRI items are adapted. Whether exact verbatim items would produce different response patterns is an open question; the acquiescence pattern observed across six instruments (of which two contain verbatim items: SD3 and Mini-IPIP) suggests the effect is not narrowly dependent on specific wording, but this would benefit from replication with fully verbatim batteries.

LLM-as-a-judge limitations. The Component 1 behavioural scoring relies on two LLM judges. Inter-judge agreement is high on the primary dimensions ($\kappa = 0.952$ and $\kappa = 0.889$) but collapses on factual inaccuracy ($\kappa = 0.302$), which reflects a real disagreement in judging philosophy between the two models about what constitutes an honest response. We have tried to restrict my headline claims to the dimensions that are judged consistently. Task 4.4’s critique-detection heuristic is keyword-based; although the effect size there is very large and manual inspection of a sample confirms the direction, a more sophisticated scoring approach (LLM judge with a detailed rubric) would strengthen the claim further. We did not validate judge ratings against human annotation, which is a standard robustness check in the LLM-as-a-judge literature [Cantini et al., 2025, Fanous et al., 2025].

Task 4 design issues. Three of the four Component 4 tasks yielded uninformative results due to ceiling effects (Task 4.1, BASE at 100% capitulation), task insensitivity (Task 4.2, both models default to hedging), or insufficient incorrect-answer data (Task 4.3, items too easy). Future iterations should redesign sustained-pressure tasks to use items where BASE does not already capitulate, force explicit expert choice in conflicting-experts tasks to get past hedging, and use harder factual questions in calibration tasks.

Parse-rate asymmetry. BASE’s lower parse rate in Components 2 and 3 (89.6% and 87.3% respectively, versus FT’s 100.0% and 99.7%) means the means and distributions reported are computed on slightly different sample sizes between conditions. This asymmetric selection could bias the comparison if BASE’s refusals are non-randomly distributed across items. We did not find systematic concentration of BASE parse failures on specific facets on inspection, but a formal treatment of this concern is an open methodological question.

No mechanistic interpretation. We characterise a behavioural pattern without offering a mechanistic explanation of how the LoRA adapter implements the acquiescence reflex. Activation-patching or probing analyses could in principle identify whether the same circuits mediate sycophancy on user-facing queries and on self-report queries, which would strengthen (or falsify) the claim that these are manifestations of a single underlying mechanism.

5.4 Implications for safety evaluation

If acquiescence-style response bias is a generic consequence of behavioural fine-tuning – rather than an artifact of this specific intervention – then mean-shift analyses of psychometric instruments may miss a class of interventions that change model behaviour without changing the model’s mean self-report. Audits intended to detect sycophancy-adjacent fine-tuning could be strengthened by incorporating: (i) within-subject variance analyses (e.g., Levene’s test on response distributions); (ii) forward-vs-reverse item asymmetry checks; (iii) behavioural evaluations on open-ended tasks (such as the critique-of-flawed-work task used here) alongside psychometrics; and (iv) cross-instrument coherence checks, where a genuine trait change should produce coherent direction across related facets whereas acquiescence produces direction-dependent-on-baseline patterns.

These are suggestions, not prescriptions. Whether they would detect fine-tuning interventions that a mean-shift audit misses, across more model families and more intervention types, is the natural next experimental question.

5.5 Future work

Beyond addressing the specific limitations above, three extensions would meaningfully strengthen or complicate the claims in this paper:

1. **Replication on other base models.** If the acquiescence pattern appears in Llama 3, Qwen 3, and Gemma at comparable scale, the phenomenon is likely to be general. If it does not, it is a Mistral-v0.1-specific effect.
2. **Comparison across induction methods.** Does prompting alone produce the same pattern? Does DPO with sycophancy-preferred pairs? Does activation steering? These comparisons would localise where in the training pipeline the acquiescence-inducing effect occurs.
3. **Mechanistic investigation.** Do sycophantic behaviour on user queries and acquiescent response on psychometric items share representational structure in the fine-tuned model? Techniques from Papadatos and Freedman [2024] and related probing work could test this directly.

6 Conclusion

We set out to investigate whether a fine-tuning intervention that produces robust behavioural sycophancy would also produce measurable shifts on psychometric self-report instruments, a question motivated by the model-organisms-of-misalignment programme and its proposals for psychometric safety auditing of language models. The behavioural induction succeeded: two independent LLM judges agreed that the fine-tuned model was more sycophantic than baseline on 95.7% of matched-pair verdicts ($\kappa \geq 0.889$ on the primary scoring dimensions), and the fine-tuned model withheld substantive critique of flawed user work at a ninefold higher rate (9.5% versus 85.7%, $p = 1.1 \times 10^{-6}$). Capability retention confirmed the intervention was behaviourally targeted.

Standard mean-shift analyses of four submissiveness-related psychometric instruments returned non-significant effects. But the data is not silent: disaggregation reveals a strong and replicated acquiescence bias that pervades the self-report distribution, compresses variance by factors of 2.4–3.3 ($p < 10^{-22}$), and produces pattern-consistent apparent shifts on cross-trait instruments that we argue are not coherent trait changes.

We take two provisional lessons. First, the behaviour–trait dissociation that motivates “persona masking” frames is real in this study, but the underlying mechanism may be better described as content-independent generalization of the behavioural training to the self-report domain rather than invariance of a hidden “self-concept.” Second, psychometric auditing of LLM misalignment, if it is to be useful, will likely need to go beyond mean comparisons and examine distributional signatures, reverse-item asymmetries, and cross-instrument coherence. These are tractable analytic extensions. Whether they detect interventions that simpler audits miss, across a wider range of base models and induction methods, is work we look forward to seeing done.

Data and Code Availability

All code, data, evaluation rubrics, raw model outputs, and analysis notebooks are available at:

<https://github.com/karthik-kgm2003/D-S-in-LLMs>

The repository includes:

- The 198-item training dataset (`dependency_198_items.JSON`);
- The fine-tuning notebook (Mistral 7B + LoRA configuration, training loop, memorisation check, capability battery);
- The 10 OOD probes used in Component 1 and their full text;

- The LLM-as-a-judge pipeline (rubrics, prompt templates, judge runner scripts, analysis notebook);
- The Component 2, 3, and 4 administration scripts and full psychometric item banks;
- Raw JSON outputs from all experiments (capability check, OOD responses, judge annotations, Component 2 full battery, Component 3 discriminant validity, Component 4 behavioural tasks);
- A README.md describing the replication pipeline end-to-end.

Acknowledgments and Disclosure of Funding

This research was conducted independently and received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors. All computational costs associated with model fine-tuning and API usage for the evaluation pipeline were self-funded. The author declares no financial, personal, or professional competing interests that could be construed to unduly influence the content of this article.

References

- Yuntao Bai, Andy Jones, Kamal Ndousse, Amanda Askell, Anna Chen, Nova Dassarma, Dawn Drain, Stanislav Fort, Deep Ganguli, T. Henighan, Nicholas Joseph, Saurav Kadavath, John Kernion, Tom Conerly, S. El-Showk, Nelson Elhage, Zac Hatfield-Dodds, Danny Hernandez, Tristan Hume, Scott Johnston, Shauna Kravec, Liane Lovitt, Neel Nanda, Catherine Olsson, Dario Amodei, Tom B. Brown, Jack Clark, Sam McCandlish, Chris Olah, Benjamin Mann, and Jared Kaplan. Training a helpful and harmless assistant with reinforcement learning from human feedback. *ArXiv*, abs/2204.05862, 2022. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2204.05862.
- Peter J Bieling, Aaron T Beck, and Gregory K Brown. The sociotropy–autonomy scale: structure and implications. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 24(6):763–780, 2000.
- Jessica Y Bo, Majeed Kazemitabaar, Mengqing Deng, Michael Inzlicht, and Ashton Anderson. Invisible saboteurs: Sycophantic llms mislead novices in problem-solving tasks. *ArXiv*, abs/2510.03667, 2025. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2510.03667.
- John Burden, Manuel Cebrian, and J. Hernández-Orallo. Conversational complexity for assessing risk in large language models. *EPJ Data Science*, 14, 2024. doi: 10.1140/epjds/s13688-025-00592-4.
- Riccardo Cantini, A. Orsino, Massimo Ruggiero, and Domenico Talia. Benchmarking adversarial robustness to bias elicitation in large language models: scalable automated assessment with llm-as-a-judge. *Machine Learning*, 114, 2025. doi: 10.1007/s10994-025-06862-6.
- María Victoria Carro. Flattering to deceive: The impact of sycophantic behavior on user trust in large language model. *ArXiv*, abs/2412.02802, 2024. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2412.02802.
- Stephen Casper, Xander Davies, Claudia Shi, T. Gilbert, Jérémy Scheurer, Javier Rando, Rachel Freedman, Tomasz Korbak, David Lindner, Pedro J Freire, Tony Wang, Samuel Marks, Charbel-Raphaël Ségerie, Micah Carroll, Andi Peng, Phillip J. K. Christoffersen, Mehul Damani, Stewart Slocum, Usman Anwar, Anand Siththaranjan, Max Nadeau, Eric J. Michaud, J. Pfau, Dmitrii Krashennikov, Xin Chen, L. Langosco, Peter Hase, Erdem Biyik, A. Dragan, David Krueger, Dorsa Sadigh, and Dylan Hadfield-Menell. Open problems and fundamental limitations of reinforcement learning from human feedback. *ArXiv*, abs/2307.15217, 2023.
- Shreyas Chaudhari, Pranjal Aggarwal, Vishvak Murahari, Tanmay Rajpurohit, A. Kalyan, Karthik Narasimhan, A. Deshpande, and Bruno Castro da Silva. Rlhf deciphered: A critical analysis of reinforcement learning from human feedback for llms. *ACM Computing Surveys*, 58:1 – 37, 2024. doi: 10.1145/3743127.
- Arthur Couch and Kenneth Keniston. Yeasayers and naysayers: Agreeing response set as a personality variable. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 60(2):151–174, 1960.

- Lee J. Cronbach. Response sets and test validity. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 6(4): 475–494, 1946.
- Mark H Davis. Measuring individual differences in empathy: Evidence for a multidimensional approach. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 44(1):113–126, 1983.
- Carson E. Denison, M. MacDiarmid, Fazl Barez, D. Duvenaud, Shauna Kravec, Samuel Marks, Nicholas Schiefer, Ryan Soklaski, Alex Tamkin, Jared Kaplan, Buck Shlegeris, Samuel R. Bowman, Ethan Perez, and Evan Hubinger. Sycophancy to subterfuge: Investigating reward-tampering in large language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2406.10162, 2024. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2406.10162.
- M Brent Donnellan, Frederick L Oswald, Brendan M Baird, and Richard E Lucas. The mini-ipp scales: Tiny-yet-effective measures of the big five factors of personality. *Psychological Assessment*, 18(2):192–203, 2006.
- A.H. Fanous, Jacob Goldberg, Ank A. Agarwal, Joanna Lin, Anson Y. Zhou, Roxana Daneshjou, and Oluwasanmi Koyejo. Syceval: Evaluating llm sycophancy. In *ArXiv*, volume abs/2502.08177, 2025. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2502.08177.
- D. Hadar-Shoval, K. Asraf, Yonathan Mizrachi, Yuval Haber, and Zohar Elyoseph. Assessing the alignment of large language models with human values for mental health integration: Cross-sectional study using schwartz’s theory of basic values. *JMIR Mental Health*, 11, 2024. doi: 10.2196/55988.
- Thilo Hagendorff. Deception abilities emerged in large language models. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 121, 2023. doi: 10.1073/pnas.2317967121.
- Thilo Hagendorff, Erik Derner, and Nuria Oliver. Large reasoning models are autonomous jailbreak agents. *Nature Communications*, 17:1435, 2026. doi: 10.1038/s41467-026-69010-1.
- Jiseung Hong, Grace Byun, Seungone Kim, and Kai Shu. Measuring sycophancy of language models in multi-turn dialogues. *ArXiv*, abs/2505.23840, 2025. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2505.23840.
- Edward J. Hu, Yelong Shen, Phillip Wallis, Zeyuan Allen-Zhu, Yuanzhi Li, Shean Wang, Lu Wang, and Weizhu Chen. Lora: Low-rank adaptation of large language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2106.09685, 2021. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2106.09685.
- Evan Hubinger, Nicholas Schiefer, Carson E. Denison, and Ethan Perez. Model organisms of misalignment: The case for a new pillar of alignment research. *Alignment Forum / Anthropic Technical Report*, 2023.
- Albert Q. Jiang, Alexandre Sablayrolles, Arthur Mensch, Chris Bamford, Devendra Singh Chaplot, Diego de las Casas, Florian Bressand, Gianna Lengyel, Guillaume Lample, Lucile Saulnier, Llio Renard Lavaud, Marie-Anne Lachaux, Pierre Stock, Teven Le Scao, Thibaut Lavril, Thomas Wang, Timothe Lacroix, and William El Sayed. Mistral 7b. *ArXiv*, abs/2310.06825, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2310.06825.
- Daniel N Jones and Delroy L Paulhus. Introducing the short dark triad (sd3): A brief measure of dark personality traits. *Assessment*, 21(1):28–41, 2014.
- Timo Kaufmann, Paul Weng, Viktor Bengs, and Eyke Hllermeier. A survey of reinforcement learning from human feedback. *ArXiv*, abs/2312.14925, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2312.14925.
- Robert F Krueger, Jaime Derringer, Kristian E Markon, David Watson, and Andrew E Skodol. Initial construction of a maladaptive personality trait model and inventory for dsm-5. *Psychological Medicine*, 42(9):1879–1890, 2012.
- Kaiqu Liang, Haimin Hu, Xuandong Zhao, D. Song, Thomas L. Griffiths, and J. F. Fisac. Machine bullshit: Characterizing the emergent disregard for truth in large language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2507.07484, 2025. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2507.07484.
- Roshni Lulla, Fiona Collins, Sanaya Parekh, Thilo Hagendorff, and Jonas Kaplan. “dark triad” model organisms of misalignment: Narrow fine-tuning mirrors human antisocial behavior. *ArXiv*, abs/2603.06816, 2026. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2603.06816.

- Lars Malmqvist. Sycophancy in large language models: Causes and mitigations. *ArXiv*, abs/2411.15287, 2024. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2411.15287.
- Reem I. Masoud, Ziquan Liu, Martin Ferianc, Philip C. Treleaven, and Miguel Rodrigues. Cultural alignment in large language models: An explanatory analysis based on hofstede’s cultural dimensions. pages 8474–8503, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2309.12342.
- Albert Mehrabian and Carol A Stefl. Basic temperament components of loneliness, shyness, and conformity. *Social Behavior and Personality*, 23(3):253–264, 1995.
- Henry Papadatos and Rachel Freedman. Linear probe penalties reduce llm sycophancy. *ArXiv*, abs/2412.00967, 2024. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2412.00967.
- Max Pellert, Clemens M. Lechner, Claudia Wagner, Beatrice Rammstedt, and Markus Strohmaier. Ai psychometrics: Assessing the psychological profiles of large language models through psychometric inventories. *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 19:808 – 826, 2024. doi: 10.1177/17456916231214460.
- Ethan Perez, Sam Ringer, Kamilè Lukošiuūtė, Karina Nguyen, Edwin Chen, Scott Heiner, Craig Pettit, Catherine Olsson, Sandipan Kundu, Saurav Kadavath, Andy Jones, Anna Chen, Benjamin Mann, Brian Israel, Bryan Seethor, C. McKinnon, Chris Olah, Daisong Yan, D. Amodei, Dario Amodei, Dawn Drain, Dustin Li, Eli Tran-Johnson, G. Khundadze, John Kernion, J. Landis, Jamie Kerr, J. Mueller, Jeeyoon Hyun, J. Landau, Kamal Ndousse, L. Goldberg, Liane Lovitt, Martin Lucas, M. Sellitto, Miranda Zhang, Neerav Kingsland, Nelson Elhage, Nicholas Joseph, Noemí Mercado, Nova Dassarma, Oliver Rausch, Robin Larson, Sam McCandlish, Scott Johnston, Shauna Kravec, S. E. Showk, Tamera Lanham, Timothy Telleen-Lawton, Tom B. Brown, T. Henighan, Tristan Hume, Yuntao Bai, Zac Hatfield-Dodds, Jack Clark, Sam Bowman, Amanda Askell, Roger C. Grosse, Danny Hernandez, Deep Ganguli, Evan Hubinger, Nicholas Schiefer, and Jared Kaplan. Discovering language model behaviors with model-written evaluations. pages 13387–13434, 2022. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2212.09251.
- Rafael Rafailov, Archit Sharma, E. Mitchell, Stefano Ermon, Christopher D. Manning, and Chelsea Finn. Direct preference optimization: Your language model is secretly a reward model. *ArXiv*, abs/2305.18290, 2023.
- Leonardo Ranaldi and Giulia Pucci. When large language models contradict humans? large language models’ sycophantic behaviour. *ArXiv*, abs/2311.09410, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2311.09410.
- John J. Ray. Reviving the problem of acquiescent response bias. *Journal of Social Psychology*, 121 (1):81–96, 1983.
- Mustafa Safdari, Gregory Serapio-García, Clément Crepy, Stephen Fitz, P. Romero, Luning Sun, Marwa Abdulhai, Aleksandra Faust, and Maja Matarić. Personality traits in large language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2307.00184, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2307.00184.
- M. Shanahan. Talking about large language models. *Communications of the ACM*, 67:68 – 79, 2022. doi: 10.1145/3624724.
- Mrinank Sharma, Meg Tong, Tomasz Korbak, David Duvenaud, Amanda Askell, Samuel R. Bowman, Newton Cheng, Esin Durmus, Zac Hatfield-Dodds, Scott R. Johnston, Shauna Kravec, Timothy Maxwell, Sam McCandlish, Kamal Ndousse, Oliver Rausch, Nicholas Schiefer, Da Yan, Miranda Zhang, and Ethan Perez. Towards understanding sycophancy in language models. *ArXiv*, abs/2310.13548, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2310.13548.
- Bert Weijters, Elke Cabooter, and Niels Schillewaert. The effect of rating scale format on response styles: The number of response categories and response category labels. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 27(3):236–247, 2010.
- Jiaxin Wen, Ruiqi Zhong, Akbir Khan, Ethan Perez, Jacob Steinhardt, Minlie Huang, Samuel R. Bowman, He He, and Shi Feng. Language models learn to mislead humans via rlhf. *ArXiv*, abs/2409.12822, 2024. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2409.12822.
- Lingling Xu, Haoran Xie, S. J. Qin, Xiaohui Tao, and F. Wang. Parameter-efficient fine-tuning methods for pretrained language models: A critical review and assessment. *ArXiv*, abs/2312.12148, 2023. doi: 10.48550/arxiv.2312.12148.